

Operator ID: fb209
Sample ID: PET (FK)
Sample Weight: 5.390 mg

PET (FK): PET-FK-1-1.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1
PET (FK): PET-FK-1-2.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1

Funktionspolymere 209

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1) Heat from 20.00°C to 300.00°C at 20.00°C/min